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Reconstruction of environmental site conditions by the integration of SCADA and reanalysis data

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Abstract. For the operational optimization of wind farms, AEP estimation and other tasks, high quality data of environmental conditions at the site are necessary. However, such data is often not available or has insufficient quality. This work tries to fill this gap, by integrating two data sources: the (usually available) operational data from the SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) system, and reanalysis data. SCADA data streams contain measurements from each wind turbine in the farm, but they are affected by various sources of uncertainty (including local flow effects, miscalibration, etc.), and might contain gaps. Meteorological reanalysis datasets can be used to fill gaps and complement SCADA data. However, modelled data can contain a wide range of biases and errors, due to limited model fidelity, coarse spatial and temporal resolution, inaccuracies in the input data feeding the model, etc. This study considers various methods to extract and merge wind speed and direction information from these diverse data sources. The analysis is based on field data measured at two experimental test sites, an offshore site equipped with 111 multi-MW turbines and a lidar buoy, and an onshore site equipped with 14 multi-MW wind turbines and a lidar. The methods are evaluated in the spectral and temporal domains by comparing the reconstructed wind characteristics with measurements from the lidars.

1. Introduction

Knowledge of the environmental conditions at wind farm sites is necessary for a range of applications, i.e. for fatigue and performance analysis or the optimization of operational procedures. Environmental wind conditions can be measured in the field using met masts or lidars. However, field campaigns are usually conducted during project planning or cover just a fraction of the operational lifetime [1]. Therefore, for applications that require environmental site conditions for longer periods of time, these conditions must be reconstructed using other available data sources. Two data sources that are usually available for most wind farm sites are: 1) operational data from the SCADA system of each wind turbine, and 2) meteorological reanalysis datasets, as for example ERA5 from the European C3S Climate Data Store (CDS) [2]. While site-specific environmental conditions can be reconstructed from SCADA only, these data sets often contain gaps. Additionally, the on-board measurements of each turbine are affected by the measurement equipment, the turbine itself and by its neighbors. On the other hand, ERA5 or similar datasets are obtained by the use of models. As such, they do not contain any gaps, but in general they will be affected by their coarse spatial and temporal resolution, and by model mismatches.

Since both datasets have different advantages and disadvantages, their integration bears the potential to mitigate their respective limitations through a synergistic effect. SCADA data can be used to identify and correct biases and mismatches in the power spectral densities of the reanalysis data. Reanalysis data,

on the other hand, can be used to fill gaps in the SCADA data streams, resulting in seamless time series of the environmental conditions that can be used for a range of wind energy applications.

This work considers different reconstruction methods of wind speed and direction based on data contained in SCADA data streams, and the u - v wind speed components available in ERA5 datasets at different height levels. For wind speed, the focus is on the reconstruction of 10-minute averaged time series with all its site-specific and spectral features, which can be used together with turbulence intensity for fatigue-related applications. For wind direction, the main challenge is to identify and correct a possible bias with respect to the meteorological coordinate system. The performance of the reconstructed and gap-filled time histories is quantified at an onshore and an offshore site by comparison with lidar measurements.

2. Reconstruction methods

In the following, different methods to reconstruct environmental conditions are defined for the two data sources SCADA and ERA5. To quantify their usability, different metrics are defined to support the choice of the most suitable method for a specific application.

2.1. SCADA

SCADA is a system for monitoring and controlling automated technical processes. Every wind turbine stores on its SCADA servers various quantities, which are usually aggregated in 10-minute mean values. SCADA streams include measurements from various sensors and status codes that inform on the operating mode of the turbine. The measurements are affected by the turbine itself and neighboring turbines, as well as by biases and other sources of uncertainty that must be accounted for before they can be used to estimate environmental conditions.

2.1.1. Wind speed. Anemometers that measure the wind speed onboard a turbine are usually located on top of the nacelle, and therefore are affected by the rotor, its wake, the proximity to the bluff-body represented by the nacelle, and possibly by the wakes of neighbouring turbines. Furthermore, the local orography can lead to an heterogenous flow at the boundaries of and within a wind plant [3, 4]. Notwithstanding these limitations, onboard anemometric measurements can be used to estimate the environmental wind speed using free-stream turbines, i.e. those not affected by the wakes released by other turbines. Here, the free-stream turbines of a wind farm for a given wind direction are determined by the use of the Floris engineering wake model [5]. A turbine i with hub height HH is defined as free-stream for a specific wind direction Γ and environmental condition X (which includes the wind speed U), if the following condition is satisfied:

$$F_i = P_{model,i}(\Gamma, X) \geq T_P \cdot P_{PC,i}(U), \quad (1)$$

where $P_{model,i}$ is the Floris-predicted power for this specific wind condition, $P_{PC,i}$ is the power from the turbine-specific power curve in correspondence to the wind speed U , and T_P is a threshold, set here to the value of 0.98. If the condition is fulfilled, F_i is set to 1, otherwise to 0. The ambient wind speed at hub height can then be estimated as the weighted average of the anemometer-measured wind speeds of all free-stream turbines with the same hub height, i.e.

$$U_{SCADA} = \frac{1}{\sum w_i F_i} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{WT}} w_i U_{HH,i} F_i, \quad (2)$$

where n_{WT} is the total number of turbines with hub height HH , and w_i is a weight attributed to each specific measurement. If the weights are all equal to 1, this expression corresponds to the arithmetic mean. However, for larger wind farms a weighting based on the distance to the location of interest may be recommended. In this study the weights are chosen to be 1 for simplicity. If the turbines have different hub heights, the measurements have to be brought to a common elevation with respect to the terrain by estimating the wind shear, which, in the absence of specific measurements, can be done by using reanalysis data (see Sect. 2.2.1). For wind farms in complex terrain or wind farms that cover a large front, the reduction to one simple ambient condition might be an excessive simplification. In such cases, a more sophisticated flow identification should be used. A possible approach to this problem was

described in ref. [6], where an heterogeneous inflow and/or intra-plant flow field is identified from SCADA data to account for changes in elevation, local surface roughness, etc. The same approach can be used to correct Eq. (1) in order to account for local speedups.

2.1.2. Wind Direction. The wind direction can be estimated using the yaw measurements γ_i of each turbine. Unfortunately, the yaw sensors are often not accurately calibrated and may contain jumps (typically after maintenance operations) or drifts over time in their signals. These effects must be corrected for, before such signals can be used to estimate the ambient wind direction. This can be achieved by a consensus-based approach, which leverages the information of neighbouring turbines to approximate the wind direction even when jumps and biases are present [7]. In this paper, jumps are manually removed by inspection of the data streams. The environmental wind direction Γ_{SCADA} is calculated as the circular mean (instead of the arithmetic one [8]) of the yaw angles of the free-stream turbines, i.e.

$$\Gamma_{SCADA}(t) = \text{atan2}\left(\frac{1}{\sum w_i F_i} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{WT}} w_i \sin(\gamma_i) F_i, \frac{1}{\sum w_i F_i} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{WT}} w_i \cos(\gamma_i) F_i\right). \quad (3)$$

However, even the circular mean of all turbine yaw angles can still exhibit an offset b_N with respect to the North. This bias can be found by minimizing the square error between the measured and the model-simulated powers for each turbine and for each of the n_t time steps t , i.e.

$$b_N = \arg \min_{b_N} \frac{1}{n_{WT} n_t} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{WT}} \sum_{t=1}^{n_t} (P_{model,i}(t, \Gamma_{SCADA}(t) + b_N) - P_{meas,i}(t))^2. \quad (4)$$

The bias-corrected wind direction can then be calculated as $\Gamma_{SCADA,c} = \Gamma_{SCADA} + b_N$.

The relative biases of the yaw signals can be corrected as well, i.e.

$$\gamma_{i,c}(t) = \gamma_i(t) - \frac{1}{n_t} \sum_{t=1}^{n_t} R_{-180,180}(\gamma_i(t) - \Gamma_{SCADA,c}(t)), \quad (5)$$

with the operator $R_{-180,180}$ that converts any angle into a range between -180 and 180 degrees.

2.2. Meteorological reanalysis (ERA5)

ERA5 is a global atmospheric reanalysis developed by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) and produced at the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). It combines model data (generated by an atmospheric model coupled with a land-surface and ocean wave model) with observations from weather stations using physical relations. ERA5 generates hourly estimates for a range of atmospheric, land and ocean climate variables. The data provides coverage of the entire Earth on a 30 km grid and at 137 horizontal model levels from the surface up to an altitude of 80 km [9]. For wind farm applications, atmospheric variables near the surface (and, here specifically, wind speed and direction) are of interest. These can be obtained by interpolating the vertical levels near the surface. Since reanalysis data can be downloaded from 1940 without gaps, ERA5 is a suitable data source to fill gaps over long periods of time. However, the data must be processed carefully to account for its coarse spatial and temporal resolution to match the conditions at a specific wind farm site.

2.2.1. Wind speed and direction. In ERA5, wind speed and direction are given in the form of the two velocity components u and v , corresponding to the eastern and northern directions, respectively. The wind speed is the resultant of the two components, i.e. $U = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}$. The meteorological wind direction is defined in a clockwise sense from 0° , which corresponds to wind coming from the true North, and can be calculated as follows:

$$\Gamma = \text{mod}\left(180 + \frac{180}{\pi} \text{atan2}(v, u), 360\right). \quad (6)$$

Since wind speed and direction in ERA5 are given at discrete heights above ground, they must be interpolated at the turbine hub height. Wind speed is corrected with the classical shear power law:

$$U_{ERA5} = U_r \left(\frac{Z_{HH}}{z_r}\right)^\alpha, \quad (7)$$

where α is the vertical shear exponent, z_{HH} is the turbine hub height, and z_r indicates the reference height (10 m for this work). The shear exponent α is calculated at each time step by least-squared fitting the wind speed values at the lowest 10 model levels, which span an altitude between 10 and 287 m, with intervals ranging from about 20 m near the ground to 45 m.

The wind direction is assumed to change linearly with height as

$$\Gamma_{ERA5} = \Gamma_r + \nu(z_{HH} - z_r), \quad (8)$$

where ν is the veer parameter that, similarly to the shear exponent, is computed by least squares fitting from the model level dataset.

Flow effects due to local terrain features are not modelled in ERA5, because of its coarse spatial resolution. To correct for this, site-specific information contained in the SCADA data is used to improve the ERA5 data. There are several statistical methods that establish a relationship between two datasets (also commonly known as Measure-Correlate-Predict). This relationship can then be used to correct the (usually long-term) time series to match the target time series [10]. Here, only a simple bias correction is applied. Assuming there is a bias that does not change with time and wind direction, the wind speed and direction are corrected as follows:

$$U_{ERA5,c}(t) = U_{ERA5}(t) - \frac{1}{n_t} \sum_{t=1}^{n_t} (U_{ERA5}(t) - U_{SCADA,HH}(t)), \quad (9)$$

$$\Gamma_{ERA5,c}(t) = \Gamma_{ERA5}(t) - \frac{1}{n_t} \sum_{t=1}^{n_t} R_{-180,180} (\Gamma_{ERA5}(t) - \Gamma_{SCADA,HH,c}(t)). \quad (10)$$

These corrections are clearly only approximate in nature. For example, as shown later on in the results, terrain-induced effects may require direction-dependent corrections. Similarly, vegetation-induced effects may add further seasonal (time) dependencies.

2.2.2. Upsampling and merging. Before the hourly ERA5 data can be merged with SCADA, it must be upsampled to the frequency of the SCADA stream (i.e. from 60 to 10 minutes). Linear interpolation may be sufficient for most atmospheric parameters. However, low-cycle fatigue damage is affected by variations in the mean wind speeds [11], which are present in the SCADA signal but not in the much smoother ERA5 signal, and that cannot be modelled by turbulence intensity.

To account for this, a spectral correction is applied to the ERA5 wind speed. The power spectral density (PSD) is defined as the product of the Fourier Transform of a given signal x and its complex conjugate:

$$PSD(\omega) = \mathcal{F}_x(\omega)\mathcal{F}_x^*(\omega) = |\mathcal{F}_x(\omega)|e^{i\phi(\omega)}|\mathcal{F}_x^*(\omega)|e^{-i\phi(\omega)}, \quad (11)$$

where $\phi(\omega)$ is the frequency-dependent phase angle. The PSD of the ERA5 signal is modified by inserting, at frequencies higher than a certain threshold ω_k , the PSD derived from the SCADA signal:

$$PSD_{syn}(\omega) = \begin{cases} PSD_{ERA5}(\omega), & \omega < \omega_k, \\ PSD_{SCADA}^*(\omega), & \omega \geq \omega_k. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The Power Spectral Density PSD_{SCADA}^* for frequencies above ω_k is approximated by an exponential function as $PSD_{SCADA}^* = a\omega^b$, where the coefficients a and b are found by a least squares fit to the PSD of the SCADA signal. By randomly sampling the new phase $\phi_{new}(\omega)$ from a uniform distribution, the Fourier Transform of a new (enriched) signal is then obtained by solving Eq. (11) for $\mathcal{F}_x(\omega)$:

$$\mathcal{F}_{x_{new}}(\omega) = \sqrt{PSD_{syn}(\omega)}e^{i\phi_{new}(\omega)}. \quad (13)$$

Applying now an Inverse Fourier Transformation, a new signal is obtained:

$$U_{ERA5,S} = \mathcal{F}_{x_{new}}^{-1} \left(\sqrt{PSD_{syn}(\omega)}e^{i\phi_{new}(\omega)} \right). \quad (14)$$

This new “enriched” signal matches the frequency characteristics of the SCADA stream above ω_k .

2.3. Performance metrics

To evaluate their performance, the reconstructed signals are compared to lidar measurements to define the corresponding errors:

$$\varepsilon = U - U_{Lidar}, \quad (15)$$

$$\varepsilon = R_{-180,180}(\Gamma - \Gamma_{Lidar}). \quad (16)$$

Assuming a normal distribution, deviations can be characterized by the systematic error (or bias) μ_ε and the random error (or standard deviation) σ_ε , where

$$\mu_\varepsilon = \frac{1}{n_t} \sum_{t=1}^{n_t} \varepsilon(t), \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_\varepsilon = \left(\frac{1}{n_t} \sum_{t=1}^{n_t} (\varepsilon(t) - \mu_\varepsilon)^2 \right)^{1/2}. \quad (18)$$

However, these statistics may not completely inform on the usability of the reconstructed signals for estimating energy yield and fatigue.

To improve on this, an energy error is defined according to the following formula:

$$\epsilon_E = \frac{E(U) - E(U_{Lidar})}{E(U_{Lidar})}, \quad (19)$$

E being the energy computed using the turbine-specific power curve for a given wind speed time series.

Fatigue, on the other hand, depends on the stress ranges that the structure experiences because of alternating loads, which are driven by wind speed variations. For fatigue applications it is therefore important to accurately model the whole wind speed spectrum. While there are suitable models for the turbulent spectrum that take the turbulence intensity as input, also the lower frequency wind speed variations (i.e. with cycle lengths of more than 10 minutes) influence fatigue [11]. To verify how well these low frequency variations in the signals are matched, a rainflow counting [12] of the reconstructed and lidar-measured wind speeds is performed and used to define the following error:

$$\epsilon_{rfc} = \frac{rfc(U) - rfc(U_{Lidar})}{rfc(U_{Lidar})}. \quad (20)$$

3. Analysis and comparison

In the following, the proposed reconstruction methods are applied to two wind farms, and their performance is evaluated by comparison with lidar measurements.

3.1. Description of the two wind plants

Figure 1 shows the geographic position of the two selected wind farms. The layout of the turbines is indicated in the boxed frames (in red for the offshore farm, and in blue for the onshore one), while the red dots correspond to the location of the lidars.

Figure 1. Geographic position of the two wind farms with their respective layouts. The red dots indicate the location of the lidars.

The offshore wind farm Anholt (indicated later on as AH) consists of 111 3.6 MW wind turbines with a hub height of 81.6 m, and it is located in the Kattegat 25 km west of the Jutland peninsula. The onshore wind farm Jever (indicated later on as JV) consists of 14 wind turbines of different types with different hub heights, and it is situated on the German mainland 20 km away from the North Sea. For the present analysis, only the turbines with a hub height of 57 m were used. The wind speeds and directions obtained from ERA5 are therefore also interpolated to these heights. While for offshore sites the terrain is simpler to model, weather stations that cover offshore sites are located farther apart than in the onshore case, which may affect the ERA5 results. Furthermore, studies have shown that the nearby coastline, as well as the presence of neighboring wind farms, may influence the local flow at Anholt [4, 13]. The wind farm Jever, on the other hand, is affected by local terrain features, including patches of trees and nearby villages that are not specifically modelled in the ERA5 dataset. Therefore, both sites present their own specific challenges when reconstructing the environmental conditions from reanalysis data.

3.2. Calibration to north of SCADA wind direction

Figure 2 presents the results of the wind direction calibration described in Sect. 2.1.2. For the Anholt wind farm, the ratio of the power of turbine P01 to the mean power of all free-stream turbines is plotted as a function of wind direction. The directions from P01 to its upstream turbines, where wake deficits are expected, are marked by green vertical lines. After a correction of -10.3° , the positions of the Floris-predicted wake deficits present a much improved fit to the measured ones. For the Jever wind farm, the figure shows the power ratio of turbine A04 and A05, indicating the directions where A04 is waked in green and where A05 is waked in red. A bias of 6.2° was identified, which here again very significantly improves the quality of the match.

Figure 2. Power ratio as a function of wind direction. Left: ratio between the power of turbine P01 and all free-stream turbines for the Anholt wind farm; right: ratio between the powers of turbines A04 and A05 for the Jever wind farm. For both farms, the bottom plots represent the probability density of wind direction.

3.3. Bias correction of ERA5 data

Due to the coarse spatial model resolution, ERA5 wind speed and direction values may exhibit rather large deviations with respect to site-specific measurements. If these deviations are systematic, they can be corrected using the available SCADA data. Figure 3 illustrates the distributions of the errors between ERA5 and SCADA-reconstructed wind speed (left plot) and wind direction (right plot). All distributions are approximately normal. For the wind speed, a greater bias and standard deviation can be observed for

the Anholt offshore wind farm than for the Jever onshore wind farm. However, the opposite can be observed for wind direction, with Jever showing a greater bias and standard deviation with a slightly skewed distribution. The bias and standard deviation are not changing significantly over time, whereas there is some dependency on wind direction. In fact, Figure 4 indicates for the Jever farm an increase of the wind speed bias for winds coming from the south to south-west. The cities of Jever and Schortens, located upstream of the farm along these directions, are presumably responsible for these effects, which are not modelled in ERA5. For Anholt, a changing wind speed and direction bias can be observed for winds coming from west to north-west with respect to the other wind directions, which corresponds to the direction of the nearby coastline.

Figure 3. Error statistics of wind speed (left plot) and wind direction (right plot) for the ERA5 model level dataset wrt. SCADA, for the two wind farms.

Figure 4. Wind speed and direction bias vs. wind direction.

3.4. Upsampling of ERA5 wind speed

As previously explained, ERA5 provides data streams at hourly intervals that, therefore, are much smoother and with different spectral characteristics than the SCADA ones, as shown in Figure 5. This is corrected with the procedure described in Sect. 2.2.2. The PSD of the wind speed U_{ERA5} (where the subscript indicates that the signal is obtained from the ERA5 model levels) is substituted at higher frequencies by the exponential function $1.88 \cdot 10^{-4} \omega^{-1.82}$, which was obtained by fitting to the PSD of U_{SCADA} , resulting in the green signal. After correction, the bottom part of the figure shows that the upsampled signal (labelled $U_{ERA5,s}$) still follows the original one (labelled U_{ERA5}), but contains also higher frequency fluctuations, similarly to the SCADA data stream (labelled U_{SCADA}).

Figure 5. Comparison among original ERA5, corrected ERA5 and SCADA wind speed data streams, over a 7-day period at Anholt. Top: PSD spectra; bottom: time histories.

3.5. Comparison to Lidar measurements

Next, the reconstructed signals are compared to lidar measurements, according to the metrics defined in Sect. 2.3. Only data points where the lidars were not affected by the farm wakes, i.e. between 220 and 320° for Anholt and 45 and 270° for Jever, were considered. The lidar measurements were averaged over 10-minute windows to match the SCADA sampling rate. For Jever, the lidar measurements were additionally filtered for outliers.

Table 1 reports the statistics for wind speed, in terms of bias μ_ϵ , standard deviation σ_ϵ , correlation coefficient ρ_{corr} , fatigue ϵ_{rfc} and energy ϵ_E errors. As expected, the bias correction of the ERA5 wind speeds (indicated by the subscript “c”) reduces the mean error for Jever. However, for Anholt there is no improvement. Since only directions from the west are considered, this can be due to the directional dependency of the bias caused by the neighboring coastline (cf. Figure 4). The standard deviation of the signal is not changed significantly by the bias correction but increases after spectral correction. Since the added fluctuations are obtained with random phases, they will unavoidably increase the standard deviation of the error and decrease the correlation ρ_{corr} with the lidar. However, the enriched signals exhibit an improved match in the spectral domain. This is indeed reflected in the rainflow counting error. In fact, while the uncorrected and bias-corrected ERA5 wind speeds exhibit large rfc errors compared to the lidar, the spectrally-corrected signals (indicated by the subscript “s”) have a much reduced rfc error. This highlights the importance of the spectral-enrichment correction of reanalysis data streams for fatigue-related applications. In addition, the energy error is also reduced after spectral correction.

Table 2 shows the statistics for wind direction. The correction of the bias in the SCADA data described in Sect. 2.1.2 leads to a reduction in the mean error for Anholt, but to an increase for Jever. The reason for this is not clear, since power estimations using Floris are much improved for the corrected wind direction (cf. Figure 2). This can be the result of a miscalibration of the lidar. However, for both farms the correlation increases with respect to the lidar wind direction. The bias correction of the ERA5 wind direction leads to a reduction of the mean error for both farms. For Anholt, both the mean error and the standard deviation are smaller than for Jever. This may be due to the more homogeneous conditions that characterize the offshore site.

Table 1. Performance metrics of the reconstructed wind speed signals from SCADA and ERA5, as compared to lidar measurements. U_{SCADA} : wind speed derived from SCADA using Eq. (2); U_{ERA5} : wind speed derived from ERA5 using Eq. (7); subscript c indicate bias correction as per Eq. (9); subscript s indicate spectral correction as per Eq. (14).

	U_{SCADA}		U_{ERA5}		$U_{ERA5,c}$		$U_{ERA5,c,s}$	
	AH	JV	AH	JV	AH	JV	AH	JV
μ_ϵ [m/s]	0.03	-0.16	-0.22	0.19	0.31	0.08	0.32	-0.17
σ_ϵ [m/s]	1.49	0.68	1.52	1.42	1.52	1.42	1.75	1.74
ρ_{corr} [-]	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.76	0.93	0.76	0.91	0.62
ϵ_{rfc} [%]	-33.05	-14.79	-71.18	-78.09	-71.11	-78.11	4.77	-20.35
ϵ_E [%]	2.48	-11.86	-3.177	20.17	4.36	14.74	3.94	-0.89

Table 2. Performance metrics of the reconstructed wind direction signals from SCADA and ERA5, as compared to lidar measurements. Γ_{SCADA} : wind direction derived from SCADA using Eq. (3); Γ_{ERA5} : wind direction derived from ERA5 using Eq. (8); subscript c indicate bias correction as per Eqs. (5) and (10)

	Γ_{SCADA}		$\Gamma_{SCADA,c}$		Γ_{ERA5}		$\Gamma_{ERA5,c}$	
	AH	JV	AH	JV	AH	JV	AH	JV
μ_ϵ [°]	8.86	0.4	-1.62	6.43	3.71	9.23	-0.78	6.04
σ_ϵ [°]	24.94	17.67	18.2	11.06	23.95	34.93	23.95	34.88
ρ_{corr} [-]	0.8	0.86	0.87	0.91	0.85	0.76	0.85	0.76

4. Conclusion and outlook

In this study, methods to integrate reanalysis and SCADA data to obtain wind conditions are explored. For SCADA datasets, the free stream turbines are used to estimate the wind speed and direction. For ERA5, the model-level data from the 10 lowest atmospheric heights ranging from 10 to 287 m are used. Several approaches are explored to correct the ERA5 wind speeds and directions for height, and to include orographic effects and missing high frequencies using SCADA data. By comparing the reconstructed signals to lidar measurements at the sites, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- For heights that deviate from the provided ERA5 single levels (10 and 100 m), use of the model levels is recommended, because of their better vertical resolution. The assumed power-law used to approximate the vertical shear should be verified, as it is possible that other profiles (e.g., logarithmic) might perform better, especially for small hub heights as in Jever.
- The wake-model-based offset identification of SCADA wind direction yielded promising results for Anholt, successfully matching the wake deficits, and improving the wind farm power prediction. For Jever on the other hand, the corrected wind direction exhibits an offset with respect to the Lidar measurements, even though the power estimations improved. This could be due to a miscalibration of the Lidar wind direction.
- The bias of the ERA5 wind direction was reduced for both wind farms; for Jever also the bias of the wind speed improved. However, a strong directional dependence of the bias can be observed (cf. Figure 4), which limits the effect of the bias correction. This becomes particularly clear when comparing with lidar data, as measurements were filtered for a specific wind direction range. Since the terrain features vary for different directions, a direction-dependent bias is necessary.
- The proposed spectral correction is able to fill the missing high-frequency characteristics of the ERA5-derived wind speed with respect to SCADA, significantly improving the rainflow counting and energy metric quality. Since this is done by generating a high-frequency component of the signal from random phases, inevitably the correlation to the lidar-measured signal decreases, which is however irrelevant for most applications. Since the additional wind

speed variations change the probability distribution of the time series, it might be useful to apply the bias correction after the spectral correction, as opposed to what was done in this work.

- For both locations, a correction of the ERA5 data is required before the data is used to fill gaps in the SCADA streams. While for wind speed the statistics are better for the onshore site, the opposite is observed for wind direction. Therefore, no conclusions can be drawn about the usefulness of the proposed methods depending on the location of the site.

Although there is certainly still room for improvement, this work represents a promising approach to reconstruct signals for applications that require seamless time series over long periods of time.

Future work will focus on improving the proposed methods to further enhance their usability for wind farm applications. This includes: testing different weighting strategies to derive ambient conditions from the free-stream turbines (see Eqs. (2) and (3)); using different vertical wind profiles for the height correction, instead of the power law adopted here; applying a direction-dependent bias correction for ERA5 data. Furthermore, the applicability to fatigue analyses and the estimation of AEP will be tested. For this purpose, aeroelastic simulations will be performed to calculate the actual turbine fatigue and energy yield from the reconstructed signals. Clearly, this first requires to further fill the signals in the turbulent range. Although this was not attempted here, this additional gap filling can be readily accomplished by the use of available turbulent wind field generators by specifying the turbulence intensity [14], yet another parameter that can be reconstructed from both SCADA and ERA5 data.

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